

On the Smarandache Pseudo-number Sequences

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Abstract The main purpose of this paper is using elementary method to study the main value of the m -th power mean of the sum of all digits in the Smarandache pseudo-number sequence, and give some interesting asymptotic formulae for them.

Keywords Smarandache Pseudo-multiple of 5, pseudo-even, pseudo-odd sequence number; Sum of digits; Asymptotic formulae.

§1. Introduction

A number is called Smarandache pseudo-multiple of 5 if some permutation of the digits is a multiple of 5, including the identity permutation. For example: 51, 52, 53, 54, 56, 57, 58, 59, 101, 102, 103, 104, 106... are Smarandache pseudo-multiple of 5 numbers. Similarly we can define the Smarandache pseudo-even numbers and the Smarandache pseudo-odd numbers. In reference [1], Professor F.Smarandache asked us to study the properties of the pseudo-multiple of 5, pseudo-even, pseudo-odd sequence. Let A denote the set of all Smarandache Pseudo-multiple of 5 numbers; Let B denote the set of all Smarandache Pseudo-even numbers and Let C denote the set of all Smarandache Pseudo-odd numbers. For convenience, denoted by $A(n)$, the sum of all the digits of the base 10 digits of n . That is

$$A(n) = \sum_{i=0}^k a_i$$

if $n = a_k 10^k + a_{k-1} 10^{k-1} + \dots + a_1 10 + a_0$. In this paper, we shall use the element method to study the mean value of the m -power of the sum of all digits in the pseudo-number sequence, and give some interesting formulae for them. That is, we shall prove the following results:

Theorem 1. For any integer number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in A \\ n \leq x}} A^m(n) = x \left(\frac{9}{2} \log x \right)^m + O(x(\log x)^{m-1}).$$

Theorem 2 For any integer number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in B \\ n \leq x}} A^m(n) = x \left(\frac{9}{2} \log x \right)^m + O(x(\log x)^{m-1}).$$

Theorem 3 For any integer number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in C \\ n \leq x}} A^m(n) = x \left(\frac{9}{2} \log x \right)^m + O(x(\log x)^{m-1}).$$

§2. Some lemmas

To complete the proof of the theorem, we need the following lemmas.

Lemma 1. For any integer number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} A^m(n) = x \left(\frac{9}{2} \log x \right)^m + O(x(\log x)^{m-1}).$$

Proof. See reference [1].

Lemma 2. For any integer number $x \geq 1$. Let D denotes the complementary set of A , then we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in D \\ n \leq x}} A^m(n) = O\left(x \frac{(\log x)^m}{\left(\frac{5}{4}\right)^{\log x}}\right).$$

Proof. From the definition of the set D , we know that the base 10 digits of the numbers in D are 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, not including 0, 5. So, there are 8^m m -digit number in D . Hence, for any integer n , there is a k such that $10^{k-1} \leq n < 10^k$. Then we have

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in D \\ n \leq x}} A^m(n) \leq \sum_{t=1}^k \sum_{\substack{10^{t-1} \leq n < 10^t \\ n \in D}} A^m(n)$$

Noting that

$$\sum_{\substack{10^{t-1} \leq n < 10^t \\ n \in D}} A^m(n) < (9t)^m \times 8^t,$$

we can write

$$\sum_{t=1}^k \sum_{\substack{10^{t-1} \leq n < 10^t \\ n \in D}} A^m(n) < \sum_{t=1}^k (9t)^m \times 8^t < 9^m \times k^m \times 8^{k+1}.$$

Since $k \leq (\log x) + 1 < k + 1$, we have

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in D \\ n \leq x}} A^m(n) = O((\log x)^m \times 8^{\log x}) = O\left(x \frac{(\log x)^m}{\left(\frac{5}{4}\right)^{\log x}}\right).$$

This proves Lemma 2.

Lemma 3. For any integer number $x \geq 1$. Let E denote the complementary set of B , then we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in E \\ n \leq x}} A^m(n) = O\left(x \frac{(\log x)^m}{2^{\log x}}\right).$$

Proof. By use the same method of proving Lemma 2, we can also get this Lemma.

§3. Proof of the theorems

Now we complete the proof of the theorems. First we prove Theorem 1. From the definition of Smarandache pseudo-multiple of 5 numbers, Lemma 1 and Lemma 2, we can get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \in A \\ n \leq x}} A^m(n) &= \sum_{n \leq x} A^m(n) - \sum_{\substack{n \in D \\ n \leq x}} A^m(n) \\ &= x \left(\frac{9}{2} \log x \right)^m + O(x(\log x)^{m-1}) - O\left(x \frac{(\log x)^m}{\left(\frac{5}{4}\right)^{\log x}} \right) \\ &= x \left(\frac{9}{2} \log x \right)^m + O(x(\log x)^{m-1}). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 1. Using the same method of proving Theorem 1, we can also deduce the other Theorems.

References

- [1] F. Smarandache, Only problem, Not Solution, Chicago, Xiquan Publ. House, 1993.
- [2] Harald Riede, Asymptotic estimation of a sum of digits, Fibonacci Quarterly, **36(1)**(1998), 72-75.